

Structural reconstruction and dual exchange bias in SrRuO₃/PrMnO₃ superlattice

Antarjami Sahoo^{*1}, Prahallad Padhan¹, and Wilfird Prellier²

¹Department of Physics, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, Chennai – 600036, India

²Laboratoire CRISMAT, CNRS UMR 6508, ENSICAEN, 6 Bd du Marechal Juin, F-14050 Caen Cedex, France

Email : lipunantarjami91@gmail.com Mob : 09962876774

Abstract:

A series of laser ablated superlattice structures with [17-u.c. SrRuO₃/n (3,4,5,.....,16)-u.c. PrMnO₃]_n have been stacked on (001)-SrTiO₃. The refinement of out-of-plane XRD patterns by DIFFaX program ensure the desired artificial fabrication. The Reciprocal Space Mapping (RSM) profiles of the superlattices reveal the stabilization of tetragonal crystal symmetry. The tetragonal symmetry manifests the larger extent of *d-p* orbital overlapping in 180° Ru-O-Mn bond, results in stronger interfacial anti-ferromagnetic (AFM) coupling between the spins of Ru and Mn ions[1]. The interplay of AFM coupling energy and Zeeman energy leads to the crossover from negative to positive exchange bias (fig-1) with the increase in cooling field for field cooled field dependent minor loops. The interfacial coupling energy for 5T cooling field was found to be 1.52 erg/cm², which is larger compared to those reported for most of the Ferromagnetic/Anti-ferromagnetic systems and 8 times of the coupling energy of La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}MnO₃/SrRuO₃, elucidating the presence of stronger AFM coupling[1].

Keywords: interface engineering, antiferromagnetic coupling, exchange bias

fig-1: Zero-field-cooled, 0.1 and 5 T field-cooled (FC) field-dependent in-plane magnetization at 20 K of (001)STO/[17 u.c. SrRuO₃/6 u.c.PrMnO₃]_n superlattice. (b) 0.1 T and (c) 5 T FC field-dependent in-plane magnetization of (001)STO/[17 u.c. SrRuO₃/8 u.c. PrMnO₃]_n.

Reference:

1. Antarjami et. al. ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces 2017, 9, 36423-36430